

PRINCIPLES AND STRUCTURE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17668800>

Abstract. *This study provides detailed information about the problems of a group of students arising from the pedagogical side in the principles and structure of psychological training in educational processes. Many of our foreign scientists have conducted research on eliminating problems in the principles and structure of psychological training. It is safe to say that the results of the research carried out using modern methods of applying psychological training in education have yielded results.*

Key words: *Psychological training, psychological methods, pedagogical methods, individual approach, methodological psychological problems, psychological exercises.*

PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARNING PRINSIPLARI VA TUZILISHI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda ta‘lim jarayonlarida psixologik treninglarning prinsiplari va tuzilishi bo‘yicha pedagogik tarafdin kelib chiqqan talabalar guruhi muammolari haqida batafsil ma‘lumotlar keltirib o‘tilgan. Psixologik treninglarda prinsiplari va tuzilishida muammolarni bartaraf etish bo‘yicha ko‘pchilik xorijiy olimlarimiz tadqiqotlarni amalga oshirgan. Psixologik treninglarni ta‘limda qo‘llashning zamonaviy usullaridan foydalangan holda amalga oshirilgan tadqiqot natijalari o‘z samarasini bergan desak yanglishmaymiz.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Psixologik trening, psixologik metodlar, pedagogik metodlar, individual yondashuv, uslubiy psixologik muammolar, psixologik mashqlar.*

Introduction

Despite the variety of psychological exercises used in psychological training sessions, the variety of teaching methods of teachers, and the variety of pedagogical methods used by psychologists in organizing psychological training sessions, it is possible to single out methodological problems in several main psychological training methods. Most of them are based on cooperative learning (i.e., students work in groups in the process of cooperative learning), which traditionally includes group discussion and situational role-playing.

In addition, researchers - theorists and practicing psychologists who solve methodological problems of psychological training - propose to include training in psychophysiological self-regulation through training in interpersonal sensitivity, including training aimed at increasing the sensitivity of students' perception in collective cooperation. It is also recommended that educational psychologists use meditative methods and stimulating (for teaching self-hypnosis)

methods in psychological training. The psychologist-trainer must make the lecture more sincere and understandable with the help of his body language, eye contact, facial expressions, and hand gestures. To make the lectures interesting, the psychologist-trainer must add positive and cheerful energy to his speech. This helps to keep the students focused.

The relationship of the psychologist-trainer with the student group is also very important, because this approach encourages learning and mutual assistance among the students. The collaborative approach includes the following aspects: Exchange of ideas and discussion: The psychologist-trainer should strive to communicate openly with students. Exchange of ideas and discussion in a group, encouraging people to express their opinions, hearing the opinion of each student, deepens the learning process. The psychologist-trainer should try to work with students, not just lecture. Often, through participation in group work, simulations and role-playing, stronger relationships are established between students. The principles and structure of psychological training are based mainly on the fact that the preparatory group discussion is a joint (collaborative) discussion of any controversial issue, which allows clarifying the opinions, positions and attitudes of group members in the process of direct communication (possibly changing, reflecting, free-thinking). Group discussion in training can also be used to give participants the opportunity to look at the problem arising in psychological training from different points of view (this allows for mutual guidance and clarification of mutual positions, which reduces resistance to accepting new information from other members of the group) and as a way to overcome the psychological methodological dilemma of group reflex through individual analysis. As a result, this experience strengthens the unity of the group and at the same time helps the participants to open their world.

We believe that there are various reasons for classifying the forms of group discussion in the implementation of psychological training in cooperative learning. In structured discussions, the main causes of methodological problems in psychological training are determined by the topic of discussion, and sometimes their order is clearly regulated. Unstructured discussions are characterized by the role of the leader in the methodology of passive psychological methodological problems, their topics are chosen at their discretion, the time for discussion is not formally limited, the conditions of psychological preparation are explained, the rules of the team are explained. In addition, in psychological training, psychologists can consider thematic discussions, in which topics that are important for all participants in the training are discussed; biographical; interactive methods, the structure and content of the relationships of group members, pedagogical and psychologically based sources are used. From discussion methods, psychological methods are used in the analysis of various situations from the life or life of the participants of the training, in the analysis of complex situations in interpersonal relationships proposed by the psychologist, and in other cases. Game methods include situational role-playing, didactic, creative, organizational-activity, imitation, business games. The use of game methods in training, according to many researchers, is considered very effective. At the first stage of group (cooperative) work, games are useful as a condition for eliminating depression and mental tension of the participants, as a condition for painless removal of psychological defenses. The game method based on psychological training very often becomes a diagnostic-based self-diagnosis tool, which allows you to easily identify difficulties in attentive communication and the presence of serious psychological problems.

Thanks to the game, the process of psychological preparation is accelerated, new behavioral skills, verbal and non-verbal communication skills are developed, and optimal ways of interacting with people around are learned. Methods aimed at developing social cognition develop the ability to perceive, understand and evaluate other people, themselves, their groups.

During the training, with the help of specially designed psychological exercises, participants receive verbal and nonverbal information about how others perceive them, how correctly they perceive themselves. They acquire the skills of deep thinking about the object of perception, semantic and psychological assessment. In e-learning, students spend a lot of time waiting. Regardless of the goal, teachers or tutors need to provide feedback on their writing and determine the level of success. They face some psychological methodological problems: they get stuck in it and the writing process is delayed. In psychological processes, completed versions; self-assessment of the work being done during the writing process becomes difficult and understanding becomes very complicated. Teachers lack a general understanding of students' psychological processes and have difficulty assessing students' understanding or collaboration. While pedagogical theories are necessary and can be partially applied in e-learning contexts, automated methods can be used with computer-based procedures. Consider the stakeholder perspective.

There are many stakeholders (students, teachers, instructors, researchers, academics) whose roles can be complemented by e-learning contexts. Their research interests may differ, overlap, or conflict. These roles may also be powerful. Methodological problems in psychological training hinder the type of tool used to analyze a given learning situation. Most tools designed to analyze software that enhances students' collaboration skills are more difficult to use by other stakeholders.

Conclusion

In psychological training, the trainer gives a brief presentation on the topic, goals and objectives of the training, and its general essence. The presentation is conducted in accordance with the topic of the training and based on the requirements for the training. Information that is used by teachers and psychologists as a means of presenting new material to train training participants can be used. The trainer conducts a psychological training lecture for those who are ready to receive new material from the training participants. In order for the participants to fully and clearly perceive the presentation, adapt to the training sessions, and also prepare for the training, the trainer conducts facilitation, psychological moderation, or role-playing games before the psychological lecture. In the processes of psychological assessment, it is important that each participant in the training actively listens to the information.

References

1. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN SHAPING THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." *Modern Science and Research* 2.10 (2023): 318-322.
2. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "Program Technology for Choosing an Effective Educational Methodology Based on Modern Pedagogical Research in The Educational System." *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS* 6.02 (2025): 30-33.

3. Turemuratova, Aziza, Zuxra Palvanova, and Laura Kazakbaeva. "RULES FOR THE TRAINER'S SELF-CONTROL WHEN CONDUCTING PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING." *Modern Science and Research* 4.6 (2025): 312-313.
4. Turemuratova, Aziza, Gulbanu Turganbaeva, and Miyassar Karimova. "PSIXOLOG-TRENERLER TOPARLARGÁ TRENIN'SHÓLKEMLESTIRIWDE TIYKARGI INDIVIDUAL PSIXOLOGIYALIQ IZERTLEWLER." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 230-235.
5. Turemuratova, Aziza, Zarafshan Risnazarova, and Maftuna Nurjanova. "TOPARLARGÁ PSIXOLOGIYALIQ TRENIN'ÓTKERIW QAÁIYDALARI HÁM PSIXOLOGIYALIQ TRENIN'TÚRLERI." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 199-205.
6. Turemuratova, Aziza, and Shaxizada Qallibekova. "PSIXOLOGIYALIQ TRENIN'METODIKASI TIYKARINDA OQIWSHILARDIÑ KOLLOBORATIV KÓNLIKPELERIN RAWAJLANDIRIW." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 187-192.
7. Turemuratova, Aziza, Tursinay Iniyatdinova, and Nilufar Saribaeva. "GRUPPA JAGDAYDA PSIXOLOGIYALIQ TRENINGLARNI SHÓLKEMLESTIRIWDIÑ TIYKARGI QAÁIYDALARI." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 193-198.
8. Turemuratova, Aziza, Shaxnoza Aralbaeva, and Asilxan Amangeldieva. "PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARNING USLUBIY MUAMMOLARI VA TRENING BOSQICHLARI." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 212-216.
9. Turemuratova, Aziza, Turg'anbay Kaypnazarov, and Atabek Embergenov. "PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARDA GURUHLAR BILAN ISHLASHNING ASOSIY TALABLARI HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 224-228.
10. Turemuratova, A. B. "TA'LIMDA PEDAGOGIK YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA O'QUVCHIYOSHLARNING KOLLOBORATIV KO'NIKMALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI." *Inter education & global study* 3.4 (2025): 242-250.